

Gain Enhancement of Star-Shaped Antenna using FSS as Reflector for C-Band Vehicular Communication Systems

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Abstract: This paper proposes a Frequency Selective Surface (FSS) reflector for C-band vehicle communications integrated with a star-shaped microstrip antenna. The proposed FSS with a star-shaped radiating element enhances gain and directivity that is crucial for vehicle communications. FSS unit cell consists of periodic arrangement of square patches and nested slots. 6 x 6 array FSS reflector is placed beneath star-shaped single element antenna and its performance is analyzed especially at 5.9GHz and 7.3GHz. It achieved an operating band from 3.35-8.34GHz for S11 < -10dB with FSS. Gain improved from 3.3dB to 9.6dB at 5.9GHz and from 3.8dB to 10.0dB at 7.3GHz. Other radiation properties and radiation efficiency are investigated at frequencies 5.9GHz and 7.3GHz. For validation of proposed FSS and star-shaped antenna for vehicle communications, results are analyzed by placing the proposed models on vehicle body.

Keywords: conformal antenna; gain enhancement; reflector; star-shaped antenna; vehicular communications.

1. Introduction

FSS are periodic structures designed to filter or reflect electromagnetic waves at specific frequencies while allowing others to pass through. When used as reflectors in antenna systems, FSS can significantly enhance the gain of an antenna by reflecting and focusing radiated energy in a desired direction, thereby improving the overall radiation efficiency. This gain enhancement is particularly useful in scenarios where the low gain of conformal microstrip antennas might otherwise limit the system's performance. In the context of vehicular communication systems, integrating FSS as reflectors offers several benefits. The use of FSS can improve the signal strength and coverage, helping vehicles maintain reliable communication over longer distances or in challenging environments such as urban areas with signal obstructions. FSS in automotive communication systems can help overcome some of the limitations of conformal microstrip antennas, enhancing performance and ensuring robust communication in critical applications.

In recent years, FSS have been widely adopted to enhance the gain of UWB antennas by acting as reflector structures. The gain improvement using FSS can be achieved through either single-layer or multi-layer configurations. Single-layer FSS reflectors function similarly to Partially

Reflective Surfaces (PRS) based on the Fabry–Perot resonator principle, where constructive interference between the direct and reflected waves results in enhanced gain. This is governed by the reflection coefficient and phase, with higher reflectivity yielding higher gain but at the cost of reduced bandwidth. Conversely, multi-layer FSS designs provide greater control over phase and reflection magnitude across a broader frequency range¹. Various researchers had worked and proposed different FSS structures for various applications. Moharamzadeh et al. developed a triple-band FSS to enhance gain of X-band triangle slot antenna, showing substantial gain enhancements at specific frequency bands, which is advantageous for high-frequency use². Chatterjee and Parui introduced a dual-band monopole antenna with corner reflector incorporating FSS, leading to enhanced directional radiation and increased gain at two frequency bands, suitable for dual-band operations³. A flexible FSS structure tailored for X-band applications is developed⁴. Ghosh and Srivastava presented a dual-band FSS with resonances that are closely spaced, using a compact unit cell that ensures angular stability and consistent performance over a wide incidence range⁵. Tahir et. al created an FSS for improving the gain of printed antennas within the Ultra-Wideband (UWB) spectrum, resulting in notable gain increases across the UWB frequency range, making it ideal for high-speed wireless applications⁶. A

wide-angle FSS with ultra-wideband characteristics is proposed for aircraft stealth applications⁷). Polarization control in FSSs and hybrid absorptive/transmissive FSS structure are discussed⁸⁻⁹). For a comprehensive perspective, a review of FSS technologies is provided¹⁰). Yuan, Xi and Zhao introduced a compact UWB FSS reflector designed to enhance gain by reflecting signals more effectively, thus reducing signal loss in wideband systems¹²).

Fernandes et. al designed a dual-band patch antenna with an FSS reflector, which significantly enhanced key parameters such as gain and efficiency, particularly in the 2.4–5.8GHz bands used in wireless communications¹³). Al-Gburi et al. developed a compact CPW-fed UWB monopole antenna using single-layer FSS reflector, achieving both a small form factor and high gain, making it suitable for UWB communication systems¹⁴). Kundu introduced an ultra-wideband FSS designed to improve antenna gain, specifically targeting ground-penetrating radar applications, with a flat design that allows for easy integration and stable performance over a broad frequency range¹⁵). Adibi et al. enhanced gain of UWB antenna with circular polarization by incorporating an FSS, achieving improvements in both gain and bandwidth while maintaining polarization stability¹⁶). Wei et. al designed a miniaturized dual-band FSS that can be applied to curved surfaces, enabling gain improvements in scenarios where traditional flat FSS structures are not practical¹⁷). A band-pass FSS and integration of FSS with antennas are presented¹⁹⁻²⁰). Naseer, Gokcen and Saka examined a stopband FSS unit cell built on textile substrates, showcasing its potential for flexible electronic applications and its capability to be integrated into wearable technologies²¹).

Kumar, De and Jain explored a modified circular loop FSS to improve gain of slot antennas, achieving significant enhancements in both gain and radiation performance²²). Catton et al. introduced a compact convoluted FSS to boost the gain of multiband antennas, enabling efficient multiband operation without compromising gain, which is ideal for portable wireless devices²³). Nakmouche et. al utilized machine learning to design a high-gain FSS-backed monopole antenna for 5G applications, achieving high performance in terms of gain and radiation efficiency while simplifying the design process²⁴). Paul, Mandal and Lalbakhsh presented a single-layer ultra-wide stopband FSS with interconnected square rings, providing effective stopband filtering and contributing to improved antenna gain in wireless systems²⁵). A single-layer FSS for 5G shielding and a star-shaped FSS are introduced²⁶⁻²⁷). Kapoor et. al reviewed the basic principles and applications of FSS as spatial filters, emphasizing their role in improving filtering and antenna gain across various systems²⁸). Shi et. al designed a dual-band antenna with an FSS to enhance gain, achieving considerable performance

improvements for dual-band operations, which are beneficial for contemporary wireless systems²⁹). Kundu, Pandey and Chatterjee introduced a quadband FSS to improve the gain of multiband antennas, with a design that maintains polarization insensitivity and angular stability, making it robust for multiband use³⁰).

Tariq et. al developed a miniaturized wideband monopole antenna with FSS for UWB systems, achieving enhanced bandwidth and gain, making it well-suited for UWB communication applications³¹). Devarapalli and Moyra proposed a CPW-fed dual-element metamaterial-inspired multiband antenna using FSS for gain improvement, offering an efficient solution for multiband applications with increased gain³²). Khan et al. created a compact FSS-based four-port MIMO antenna with reduced mutual coupling, addressing the challenge of minimizing interference while enhancing gain in MIMO systems³³). Arif et. al introduced a split-center resonator FSS to boost the gain of a CPW-fed UWB antenna, achieving high-gain performance while maintaining wideband characteristics, making it ideal for UWB communications³⁴). Das, Rajput and Mukherjee proposed a bandstop filter based on FSS for both TE and TM polarizations, contributing to improved filtering in electromagnetic compatibility applications³⁵). Enhancement of UWB antenna performance using FSS reflectors is investigated³⁶).

This paper presents a novel FSS as reflector to enhance the radiation properties of conformal star-shaped antenna³⁸) for C-band vehicle communication applications. Section 3 describes unit cell analysis of proposed FSS as reflector. FSS with conformal star-shaped antenna³⁸) for gain enhancement is presented in Section 4. Section 5 depicts the placement of antenna and FSS on vehicle and its results analysis. State of art literature comparison is also tabulated in Section 5. Section 6 gives the conclusion of the work proposed.

2. FSS unit cell design

FSS unit cell shown in Figure 1(a) consists of a periodic arrangement of square patches and nested slot geometries. The structure is designed to act as a reflective surface to enhance performance of antenna by selectively reflecting electromagnetic waves within specific frequency band (C-band). It is composed of square patch, nested slots and gaps. The central square patch (s1) is the primary resonant element. It defines the main resonant frequency of unit cell. Overall dimensions of the unit cell are defined by Lu and Wu. Smaller square slots (nested slots) are placed inside and around the patch. These slots (s2) alter the electromagnetic response, introducing additional resonances and improving bandwidth. The gaps between the patches and surrounding slots (g1 and g2) play a key role in tuning resonance characteristics of FSS. It is designed on Polyimide substrate of thickness 0.2mm.

(b) Simulation view in HFSS
Fig. 1: Proposed FSS unit cell

Table 1: Dimensional specifications of FSS unit cell

Parameter	L_u	W_u	s_1	s_2	g_1	g_2
Dimensions (mm)	9	9	3	1	0.4	0.5

The design parameters and dimensions are provided in Table 1. Figure 1(b) shows unit cell design implemented in HFSS. Master-Slave Boundaries along the X and Y axes are defined. These conditions simulate an infinite array by ensuring that the electromagnetic fields on one side of the boundary match those on the opposite side. The design setup includes Floquet Port applied along the Z-axis and bottom surface is complete ground that acts as reflector. Two modes are defined in Floquet port: Mode 1 TE(0,0) and Mode 2 TM(0,0).

2.1. S-parameters of unit cell

Figure 2(i) illustrates S-parameter characteristics of FSS unit cell in ang-deg. $S(\text{FloquetPort1:1}, \text{FloquetPort1:1})$: refers to the reflection coefficient (S11) for Mode 1 (TE(0,0)). $S(\text{FloquetPort1:2}, \text{FloquetPort1:1})$: refers to the transmission coefficient (S21) between Modes 1 (TE(0,0)) and 2 (TM(0,0)). $S(\text{FloquetPort1:2}, \text{FloquetPort1:2})$: refers to the reflection coefficient (S22) for Mode 2 (TM(0,0)). Across the frequency range, the S-parameters show a relatively flat response. This stability indicates that FSS structure is well-designed to operate across the entire band, ensuring predictable performance in terms of phase and reflection. The reflection coefficients (S11 and S22) for TE mode and TM mode remain close to 180°, signifying efficient reflection with minimal phase deviation across the

band. This reflects FSS effectiveness in serving as a reflector for C-band. Transmission coefficients S21 and S12 between TE and TM modes is consistent, staying around -90° to -100°.

The low phase variation between modes implies that minimal energy is transferred between polarizations, a desired characteristic when the goal is reflection rather than mode conversion. The use of both TE and TM modes ensures that FSS can handle both polarizations, making it suitable for diverse applications such as satellite and vehicular communications that might use dual-polarized antennas. Reflection phase characteristics (deg) of proposed FSS unit cell are illustrated in Figure 2(ii). The curve is slowly decreasing from about 179.6° at 3 GHz to 177.4° at 10 GHz. It is close to +1800 throughout the band. Stability in phase reduces beam distortion and with minimal phase shift it supports in-phase reflection. Therefore, the proposed FSS unit cell acts as good reflector for gain enhancement of broadband antenna.

(i) S-parameter characteristics of proposed unit cell

(ii) Reflection phase characteristics of proposed FSS unit cell

Fig. 2: S-parameter characteristics

2.2. Equivalent circuit model of FSS unit cell

Proposed FSS unit cell equivalent circuit model in L, C components is presented in Figure 3. From FSS unit cell structure, central square ring and small inner squares lead

to inductive behavior and the gaps between square loops g_1 and g_2 introduce capacitive effects. ADS software is used to design equivalent circuit. Figure 3(i) represents LC equivalent circuit and Figure 3(ii) illustrates S_{11} phase response characteristics obtained from LC equivalent circuit simulation in ADS tool.

(a) LC equivalent circuit model of FSS unit cell

(b) S_{11} phase response characteristics

Fig. 3: Equivalent circuit model of FSS unit cell

3. FSS with Star Shaped Conformal Antenna

Figure 4 represents placement of 6×6 array FSS reflector with star shaped antenna³⁸). The star-shaped antenna is positioned in front of the FSS array, and FSS is placed at a specific distance 'd' from antenna to maximize its performance. The combination of FSS and antenna enhances gain by reflecting electromagnetic waves back towards antenna, focusing radiated energy more effectively.

(i) Side view (ii) Top view

Fig. 4: Placement of 6×6 array FSS as reflector with star-shaped antenna

3.1. Optimization of distance of separation

Fig. 5: S_{11} characteristics of antenna with FSS for various values of 'd'

Figure 5 illustrates reflection coefficient (S_{11}) characteristics of antenna integrated with FSS reflector for various distances ('d') between antenna and FSS. The curves show S_{11} values for different distances: 9mm, 11mm, 13mm and 15mm. Each curve demonstrates how the impedance matching of antenna changes as distance between antenna and FSS is altered. At $d = 11$ mm, S_{11} curve shows the most significant dip in reflection, indicating better impedance matching at the target frequencies.

Figure 6 shows peak gain characteristics of star-shaped antenna with FSS for different values of separation distance 'd' between antenna and FSS. As the distance 'd' increases, the peak gain of antenna tends to decrease. The optimal separation distance for maximum gain appears to be at 11mm. Peak gain (dB) values for different frequencies at various distances "d" are tabulated in Table 2.

Fig. 6: Peak gain characteristics of antenna with FSS for different values of 'd'

Table 2: Peak gain values at different frequencies

Frequency (GHz)	9mm	11mm	13mm	15mm
3.8	7.182	7.05296	7.26643	7.25439
5.9	9.35635	9.55214	9.02575	8.52916
7.3	9.62954	9.98713	8.94731	7.92882
8	9.39657	10.03964	8.4973	7.86482
4.2	7.85175	7.79319	7.8524	7.75655

3.2. S11 characteristics

Figure 7 illustrates S11 characteristics of antenna with and without FSS. The graph compares S11 of simulated with and without FSS and measured with FSS characteristics. The antenna performance improves with FSS integration, as indicated by the shifts and deeper notches in the S11 curve for both simulated and measured data. The operating band (S11 $\leq -10\text{dB}$) without FSS is 3.95 – 8GHz and with FSS is 3.35 – 8.34GHz. The results from both simulations and measurements with FSS display clear enhancements when compared to the configuration without FSS. This highlights the benefits of implementing FSS for improving gain and expanding bandwidth, particularly within the C-band frequencies.

Fig. 7: S₁₁ characteristics of antenna with and without FSS

3.3. Surface current distribution

Figure 8 illustrates current distribution of antenna with and without FSS array at 5.9GHz and 7.3GHz resonant frequencies. From these Figures it is observed that proposed FSS structure acts as reflector and hence it enhances gain of the antenna.

Fig. 8: Current distribution of star shaped fractal antenna

3.4. Far-field radiation characteristics

3D gain plots of star-shaped antenna with and without FSS at 5.9GHz and 7.3GHz frequencies are illustrated in Figure 9(i)-(iv). At 5.9GHz frequency, gain is enhanced by 6.3dB with FSS and at 7.3GHz frequency gain is enhanced by 6.2dB. It is observed from the Figures that backward radiation is directed towards major beam due to placement of FSS and directivity is also improved.

Fig. 9: 3D gain plots of antenna with and without FSS at different frequencies

The polar plot Figure 10(i)-(iv) illustrate the radiation patterns of antenna at 5.9GHz and 7.3GHz with and without FSS in E and H-planes. Minor discrepancies between simulated and measured data are seen, which can

be attributed to practical factors like measurement setup or slight deviations in antenna and FSS fabrication. Figure 10(i) represents E-plane patterns at 5.9GHz with and without FSS. Beamwidth has reduced from 1000 to 650 due to FSS placement. Gain and directivity have enhanced. Figure 10(ii) illustrates H-plane patterns at 5.9GHz with and without FSS. The pattern is broader and less directed, typical of a standard patch antenna without FSS. It shows a wide beamwidth with relatively low gain, indicating a more omnidirectional radiation pattern in H-plane. The pattern with FSS is more focused with a significantly narrower main lobe, showing a directional nature with enhanced directivity. Side lobes are present but less pronounced compared to E-plane, maintaining most of radiation energy within the main lobe. Similarly, Figures 10(iii) and (iv) present radiation patterns at 7.3GHz in E and H-planes respectively. Proposed FSS reduces beamwidth and improves gain and directivity of antenna.

(i) E-Plane at 5.9GHz

(ii) H-Plane at 5.9GHz

(iii) E-Plane at 7.3GHz

(iv) H-Plane at 7.3GHz

Fig. 10: Radiation patterns at different frequencies

Figure 11 illustrates peak gain characteristics of star-shaped antenna with and without FSS across a frequency range. Proposed FSS significantly enhances the peak gain of antenna, with an increase of about 6.3dB across the frequency range compared to antenna without FSS. Measured results closely match simulated gains, indicating practicality and effectiveness of FSS in improving antenna performance, particularly for high-gain applications in C-band applications. Table 3 gives the comparison of peak gain (dB) values with and without FSS for various frequencies.

Fig. 11: Peak gain characteristics of antenna with and without FSS

Table 3: Peak gain (dB) values with and without FSS

Frequency (GHz)	Without FSS (dB)	With FSS (dB)	Gain improvement (dB)
3.8	1.04	7.05	6.01
4.2	1.60	7.79	6.19
5.9	3.11	9.55	6.44
7.3	3.47	9.98	6.51
8	3.67	10.03	6.36

Fig. 12: Radiation efficiency characteristics of antenna with and without FSS

Figure 12 shows radiation efficiency characteristics of antenna with and without FSS. Both the simulated and experimental results specify a substantial enhancement in performance due to FSS, making the antenna more efficient for practical applications. Radiation efficiency values at different frequencies with and without FSS are tabulated in Table 4.

Table 4: Radiation efficiency with and without FSS

Frequency (GHz)	Without FSS	With FSS
3.8	0.96455	0.98692
4.2	0.96607	0.98824
5.9	0.9706	0.98612
7.3	0.97141	0.98961
8	0.9699	0.97802

4. Antenna with FSS placed on the vehicle

To validate the proposed FSS and star-shaped antenna for vehicle communications, antenna with FSS is placed on side mirror and simulated in ANSYS SAVANT tool to analyze its performance. Figure 13 presents a 3D radiation pattern (5.9GHz) of antenna mounted on vehicle, depicting the gain distribution in the far-field region surrounding the car. The primary radiation lobe is oriented towards the front and sides of the vehicle, suggesting strong forward-directed radiation. There are noticeable side lobes extending towards the sides of the vehicle, but these are at a lower gain level compared to main lobe.

Fig. 13: Placement of antenna with FSS on vehicle

Figure 14(i)-(iii) display polar plots of gain pattern for vehicle-mounted antenna system, highlighting the gain characteristics in decibels (dB) for two polarization states: total composite polarization and incident composite polarization in three different planes XY, YZ and XZ. The antenna system exhibits strong forward-directed gain, making it highly suitable for V2V and forward-looking communications. Side and rear gains are significantly lower, which is typical for vehicle-mounted antennas due to structural obstructions.

(i) YZ plane

(iii) XY plane

Fig. 14: Radiation patterns of antenna placed on vehicle at 5.9GHz

(ii) XZ plane

Figure 15 and Figure 16 illustrate gain characteristics and radiation efficiency characteristics with FSS when mounted on vehicle and without vehicle. Gain and radiation efficiency are slightly dropped when mounted on vehicle due vehicle body metallic effects and complex platforms like vehicle.

Fig. 15: Gain characteristics with FSS

Fig. 16: Radiation efficiency characteristics with FSS

Fig. 17: Placement of star-shaped antenna with FSS on vehicle

Fig. 18: S₁₁ characteristics with FSS

Figure 17 illustrates experimental setup used to validate the performance of proposed FSS and star-shaped antenna for C-band vehicle communications. Antenna with FSS is placed on front glass of vehicle as shown in Figure 17 with vector network analyzer. Figure 18 presents S₁₁ characteristics of proposed FSS with star-shaped antenna with and without placement on vehicle. Though the characteristics slightly deviated when mounted on vehicle, still antenna performs for C-band communications.

5. Comparison

Proposed FSS reflector with star-shaped antenna performance metrics like gain, radiation efficiency, operating band, bandwidth, substrate, its dielectric

constant and loss tangent comparison with other relevant works are tabulated in Table 5.

Table 5: Comparison of proposed model with other relevant works

Ref. No.	Dimensions (mm)	Operating Bands (GHz)	Bandwidth (GHz)	Gain (dB)	Radiation Efficiency (%)
5)	45 × 45	3.1 - 10.6	7.5	9.2	90
11)	50 × 50	3.5 - 7.5	4	7.5	> 88
13)	30 × 30	3.6 - 6.1	2.5	7.87	> 94
15)	50 × 50	5.53 - 6.36	0.83	8.98	> 95
18)	40 × 40	1.5 - 3.5	2	6.5	85
22)	35 × 35	3.5 - 7.5	4	7.5	> 88
24)	45 × 45	3.1 - 10.6	7.5	9.2	90
36)	50 × 50	2.2 - 12.7	10.5	11.5	89
37)	26 × 26	2.638-11.8	9.162	7.6	93
This work	45 x 45	3.35 - 8.34	4.89	10	98.9

6. Conclusion

A compact and novel FSS reflector is proposed to enhance radiation properties of a conformal star-shaped antenna. FSS unit cell analysis presented and FSS 6 x 6 array is placed beneath star-shaped antenna to analyse its performance. It achieved an operating bandwidth of 4.89GHz from 3.35 – 8.34GHz. 3D gain and radiation patterns are examined at 5.9GHz and 7.3GHz frequencies. Gain and radiation properties are improved with FSS. The proposed model is mounted on vehicle and analysed to validate vehicle communication applications. With enhanced radiation properties and operating band, the proposed model is well suitable for C-band communication applications.

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